

MODELS OF PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation: The article reveals the concept of the model and the style of pedagogical communication in the educational process

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Currently, on the pages of psychological and pedagogical literature, much attention is paid to the problem of communication in professional pedagogical activity.

Education is essentially a communicative process, the basis of which is communication: through communication, the educator organizes the behavior and activities of students, evaluates their work and actions, informs about events, causes appropriate feelings about misconduct, helps to overcome difficulties, not to lose faith in their abilities.

It is more difficult to talk to a child than to an adult: to do this, you need to be able to correctly perceive the external manifestations of his contradictory inner world, take into account the possible emotional reaction to the word addressed to him. Communication is carried out not only in verbal form. A look, a gesture, a pose, even silence is also an answer or an appeal to a partner.

Pedagogical communication is a professional communication between the educator and the students having certain pedagogical functions and aimed at creating a favorable psychological climate, as well as optimizing the relationship between the teacher and the students within the student body.

Pedagogical communication is aimed not only at the interaction itself, and at students for their personal development, but also at what is basic for the pedagogical

system itself — the organization of the educational process and the formation of skills on this basis.

Pedagogical communication — interaction, cooperation of the educator and students. This is a personal and socially oriented interaction.

Models of pedagogical communication.

Communication is a process of development and formation of relations between subjects who actively participate in the dialogue. The teacher's speech is the main means that allows him to introduce students to his ways of thinking. If we consider communication as a cross-cutting process, then it is necessary to distinguish two main models of communication: educational and disciplinary; personality-oriented.

1. Educational and disciplinary model of communication. It has been developing in our country for decades and bears the imprint of the second half of the 70s of the last century, when the purpose of training was to equip students with knowledge, skills and abilities. The slogan during the interaction of an adult with children was "Do as I do". The model of communication under consideration is characterized by an authoritarian style of communication where: Methods of communication: instructions, explanations, prohibitions, demands, threats, punishments, notations, shouting. Communication tactics: dictate or guardianship. There is a view of the child only as an object of the application of the forces of the educational system. As a result of such a communication model, a detrimental effect on the child's personality occurs. An alternative to this model is a personality-oriented communication model.

2. A personality-oriented model of communication. The purpose of the personality-oriented communication model is to provide a sense of psychological security of the child, his trust in the world, the joy of existence, the formation of the beginning of personality, the development of the child's individuality.

This model of communication is characterized by a dialogical style of communication. This model of communication is characterized by the fact that an adult interacts with a child in the process of communication. It does not adjust the

development of children, but prevents the occurrence of possible deviations in the personal development of children. The formation of knowledge, skills and abilities is not a goal, but a means of full-fledged personal development. Methods of communication: understanding, recognition and acceptance of the child's personality, based on the ability to decentralize that is being formed in adults (the ability to take the position of another, take into account the child's point of view and not ignore his feelings and emotions).

Communication tactics: cooperation, creation and use of situations requiring the manifestation of intellectual and moral activity of children. The personal position of the teacher: to proceed from the interests of the child and the prospects for his further development. In this regard, in modern science and practice, the concept of the pedagogical process as a dialogue is becoming increasingly recognized, providing for mutually directed and conditioned interaction of participants in this process, as well as methods of group discussion. In this regard, pedagogical communication acts as the main mechanism for achieving the main goals of education and upbringing.

Pedagogical communication style.

Pedagogical communication is carried out in various forms, depending mainly on the individual qualities of the teacher and his idea of his own role in this process. In psychological and pedagogical literature, this problem is usually considered in connection with the style of pedagogical activity. There are several classifications of pedagogical styles based on different grounds. For example, regulated and improvisational styles of pedagogical interaction are distinguished as opposed to each other, which can also be considered as styles of pedagogical communication. The regulated style provides for strict division and limitation of the roles of participants in the pedagogical process, as well as following certain patterns and rules. Its advantage, as a rule, is in the clear organization of educational work. However, this process is characterized by the emergence of new, unexpected conditions and circumstances that are not provided for by the original regulation and cannot be "adjusted" to it without conflict. Improvisational style in this regard has a

significant advantage, as it allows you to spontaneously find a solution to each newly emerging situation. The advantages of a particular style are debatable; a harmonious combination of elements of regulation and improvisation in the pedagogical process seems optimal, which allows you to simultaneously meet the necessary requirements for the process and the result of educational work, as well as, if necessary, adjust the mechanisms of interaction.

In the style of pedagogical communication, the peculiarities of the communicative capabilities of the teacher, the established nature of the relationship between him and the pupils, the creative individuality of the teacher, as well as the individual characteristics of children are manifested. The communication style inevitably reflects the general and pedagogical culture of the educator and his professionalism.

Different styles of communicative interaction give rise to several models of behavior of the educator in communicating with students.

The first model. The teacher seems to rise above the class. He soars in the world of knowledge, science, is passionate about them, but is at an unattainable height. Here the communication system develops as follows: the teacher is, as it were, detached from the students, they are only perceiving knowledge for him. As a rule, such a teacher is little interested in the personality of the child and his relationship with him, reducing pedagogical functions to the communication of information. Only the process of information transfer is important to him, and the student acts only as a "general context" for science.

It is necessary to take into account the negative consequences that such a model of communication entails. First of all, this is the lack of psychological contact between the teacher and the children.

Model two. The meaning of this rather common model of communication is that between teachers and children, the distance that the teacher sets between himself and the students acts as an invisible limiter in the relationship. Such constraints can serve as: – the teacher's emphasis on his superiority over the students; – the predominance of the desire to communicate information, not to teach; – lack of

desire for cooperation. The results of such communication are the lack of interpersonal contact between the teacher and the children, weak feedback, indifference of students to the educator. It is necessary to move away from such a model of relationships.

The third model. Its essence is that the teacher builds relationships with children selectively. In particular, he concentrates his attention on a group of students (strong or, conversely, weak), as a locator, catches these children, leaving the rest without attention. The reasons for this attitude may be different: – the teacher is passionate about children who are interested in something, gives them special tasks, involves them in clubs and elective work, without paying attention to others; — does not know how to combine a frontal approach with an individual one. As a result, an integral and continuous communication system is not created: it is replaced by fragmentary, situational interaction.

Model four. The teacher, in the process of interacting with students, hears only himself: when explaining the material, during individual conversations with children. The teacher is absorbed in his thoughts, ideas, pedagogical tasks, does not feel communication partners.

The danger of such a model of communication is that such a significant feedback in communication for education is lost here, without which it is not possible to effectively manage the educational process. The consequences of such a model of communication are as follows:

- the teacher does not perceive the psychological atmosphere in the classroom;
- the educational effect of interaction with students decreases.

The fifth model. The teacher directly and consistently acts on the basis of a planned program, ignoring the changing circumstances that require a change in communication.

Such kind of teacher seems to be doing everything right: he has a well-founded plan, correctly formulated tasks. But he does not take into account that the pedagogical reality is constantly changing, new conditions arise that must be immediately captured by him and cause corresponding changes in the

methodological and socio-psychological arrangement of education and training. What is the danger of such a model of pedagogical behavior? In the course of the educational process, two lines are clearly distinguished: the first is ideal, planned and the second is real. For such a teacher, these lines do not intersect.

As a result, well-planned types and forms of work remain unfulfilled, give a low pedagogical effect.

Model six. The teacher is tormented by constant doubts: whether he is understood correctly, correctly, whether this or that remark is interpreted, whether they are offended.

As a result, the teacher is concerned not so much with the content side of the interaction as with the relational aspects. The teacher constantly doubts, hesitates, analyzes, which, ultimately, can lead to neuroses. Carefully observe yourself and, if there is such a "self-examination", strive to get rid of it.

Model seven. Friendly characteristics prevail in the system of relationships. The teacher is in dialogue with the students, keeps them in a positive mood, encourages initiative.

The style of interaction of a teacher with children has a direct impact on the nature of children's communication with each other, the general atmosphere in the classroom. So, if a teacher demonstrates a respectful attitude towards children, supports the initiative, shows interested attention, helps in difficult situations, then it is highly likely that children will communicate with each other according to the same rules. On the contrary, the authoritarian attitude of the teacher towards children, the suppression of independence, the presence of negative assessments concerning the personality, and not the actions of the child, can lead to low group cohesion, frequent conflicts between children, and other difficulties in communication.

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